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A Comparative Study on Adjustment amongst Senior Secondary School Students in Sikkim

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Abstract

This investigation aimed to study how senior secondary school students in the eastern districts of Sikkim cope with different challenges and changes, with a particular focus on gender differences. The core objectives were to study the emotional, social, and educational adjustments of these students concerning their gender. Data were collected from 94 senior secondary students in Sikkim using a standardized tool consisting of 48 items grouped into five factors and the study is confined to the eastern districts of Sikkim. Arithmetical analyses were conducted using Mean, Standard Deviation (S.D), and 't' ratios to examine the collected data. The study revealed significant findings, allowing the researchers to draw certain results and conclusions.

Keywords: *Adjustment, emotional adjustment, social adjustment, and educational adjustment.*

Adjustment is regarded as an important factor in every individual's life. It is the process of being familiarized with a given environment. With regard to school-going students, it is important to understand the role of being a student and to adjust to numerous features of the school setting. It is a pre-requisite condition for content and healthy life. **Lakhani (2017)** In a school setting child progress and achievement plays an important role and it is also effective in their attitudes with regard to school, their anxieties, aloneness, social sustenance, academic enthusiasm, and interpersonal relationship.

Shaffer (1961) "Adjustment is the process by which a living organism maintains a balance between its needs and the circumstances that influence the satisfaction of these needs" (as cited in Aggarwal, 2005).

The above explains that adjustment is a fundamental process that living organisms, including humans, engage in to achieve a state of balance between their internal needs and the external circumstances that influence the satisfaction of those needs. It encompasses the continuous effort of individuals to adapt and cope with various challenges and demands presented by their environment. This process requires aligning personal requirements, such as emotional, social, and physical needs, with the resources available in the surrounding environment. Successful adjustment entails finding a harmonious fit between what an individual needs and the conditions they encounter. It is an ongoing and dynamic process, as the environment and individual needs constantly change. Effective adjustment allows individuals to function optimally, maintain well-being, and thrive in their daily lives. It is a crucial aspect of human development and plays a significant role in shaping how individuals interact with and respond to the world around them.

Role of Adjustment in Education

Adjustment plays a crucial role in every individual's life, and its significance is particularly pronounced in the educational setting. For students, making necessary adjustments is essential for achieving various aspects of their lives. Social and cultural adjustments are equally important in fostering comfort within their surroundings and meeting their psychological needs through social connections. As people become more familiar and at ease with their environments, they engage in interpersonal activities to fulfill their arising needs, especially in new or changed situations. Students face a multitude of demands in school, and it goes beyond just academic concerns as they are equally influenced by social and emotional changes. Adapting to the new school environment requires students to address their concerns directly with teachers. In terms of academic adjustment, students must become independent learners to cope with the new academic demands. However, present-day students encounter challenges such as managing heavier academic workloads, keeping pace with peers in class, and struggling to comprehend diverse teaching strategies and techniques used by teachers, leading to adjustment problems among them.

Devika. R (2014) conducted a study focusing on senior secondary school students and their levels of adjustment. The research findings revealed that, on the whole, secondary school students displayed an average level of adjustment. However, when exploring the data further, it was observed that there was a notable difference in emotional adjustment based on gender. This implies that male and female students might handle their emotions and psychological well-being differently. On the other hand, no significant differences were found between genders concerning family, social, educational, and financial adjustment. This suggests that both male and female students were generally capable of adapting to their family, social, and academic environments, as well as managing their financial situations similarly. Overall, the study contributes valuable insights into the adjustment patterns of senior secondary school students and highlights the importance of considering gender-specific emotional aspects in educational and psychological interventions.

Jain and Pasrija (2014) conducted a study aimed at examining the emotional maturity and adjustment levels of school-going students. The researchers gathered data from a sample of 140 students using a simple random sampling method. The investigation delved into whether there were any significant differences in emotional maturity and adjustment between students attending government schools and those in private schools, as well as between boys and girls. The findings of the study revealed that there were no notable differences in emotional maturity and adjustment levels among the students based on the type of school they attended (government or private) or their gender (boys or girls). This implies that both government and private school students, as well as boys and girls, demonstrated similar levels of emotional maturity and ability to adjust to their school environments. These results provide valuable insights for educators and policymakers, highlighting the need for comprehensive support and interventions that cater to emotional development and adjustment for all school-going students, regardless of their school type or gender.

Sinha V.K. (2014) conducted a research study focusing on college-going students to explore the potential connection between emotional maturity and adjustment. The study involved a sample of 200 students, selected through a random sampling procedure to

ensure representation from the college population. Through the investigation, the researcher sought to examine whether emotional maturity and adjustment were related in any significant way among these students. The results of the study revealed a positive relationship between emotional maturity and adjustment, indicating that as students' emotional maturity levels increased, so did their ability to adapt and adjust effectively to various challenges and situations in the college environment. This finding suggests that students with higher emotional maturity may experience greater ease in managing academic and social aspects of college life, potentially leading to overall well-being and academic success. The study contributes valuable insights into the importance of emotional maturity in the context of college life and underscores the potential benefits of nurturing emotional development to enhance students' overall adjustment and college experience.

Mahmood et al (2015) The primary objective of the study was to investigate how teenagers cope with their emotions and how this relates to their academic performance. The researchers also sought to identify potential gender differences in this aspect. The study analyzed data from a sample of adolescents, examining their emotional adjustment and academic achievement, particularly focusing on their O' level examination results. Surprisingly, the findings indicated that students who passed their O' level exams tended to have lower emotional adjustment levels compared to their peers who did not pass. This suggests that academic success might come at the expense of emotional well-being for some students. Furthermore, the study revealed significant differences in emotional adjustment between students who passed their exams and those who did not. Additionally, the research found that girls generally exhibited better emotional adjustment than boys. This gender difference implies that girls may be more adept at handling their emotions effectively in the context of their academic pursuits. The study contributes valuable insights into the complex relationship between emotional adjustment and academic achievement among adolescents, emphasizing the importance of addressing emotional well-being alongside academic performance to ensure holistic development during this critical life stage.

Gehlawat (2018) conducted a study on school students to explore how boys and girls adapt to their surroundings. The research involved 471 students, with 234 being boys and 237 being girls, selected randomly. The results showed no significant differences in relation to boys and girls in terms of their social behavior, emotions, and academic performance.

Neelavathi and Emimah (2019) conducted “a study on the adjustment of arts and science college students in relation to their social intelligence”. they looked at how well arts and science college students adapted to college life based on their social intelligence. The researchers examined the connection between social intelligence and college adjustment, considering factors like gender, chosen subject, and college location. The study involved 250 undergraduate students from Thoothukudi District. To measure social intelligence and adjustment, the researchers used a scale that they had created and validated. The findings showed significant differences in how humanities and science students adjusted to college, depending on their gender and the location of the college.

Importance of the Study : The study on the need and importance of students' adjustment in the east districts of Sikkim holds significant value due to several reasons:

Unique Educational Landscape: Sikkim's educational landscape presents a unique blend of monastic education and formal schooling. Investigating this duality can offer valuable lessons for educational policymakers on how to maintain and integrate diverse educational approaches, catering to the needs of different student populations.

Empowering Students for a Changing World: As the world rapidly evolves, students need to be aware of global happenings and become adaptable to new challenges. The study can assess how well the current education system prepares students for the contemporary world, including skills like critical thinking, problem-solving, and adaptability.

Identifying Adjustment Challenges: With a focus on learners' adjustment problems, the study can pinpoint specific issues faced by students in the educational environment. Recognizing and addressing these challenges can contribute to enhancing overall student well-being and academic performance.

Improving Academic Achievement: By investigating the relationship between adjustment and academic achievement, the study can shed light on how students' emotional and social well-being impacts their learning outcomes. This understanding can lead to the development of targeted interventions to improve academic performance.

Policy and Curriculum Enhancements: Research findings can guide educational policymakers in tailoring policies and curricula to suit the needs of students in Sikkim's east districts. This ensures that the education system aligns with the cultural context and fosters a positive learning environment.

Long-term Development: As education plays a vital role in a region's socio-economic development, the study's outcomes can contribute to the long-term progress of Sikkim's east districts. Better education and student adjustment can lead to a more skilled and productive workforce, fostering overall economic growth and societal well-being.

In conclusion, the study on education and students' adjustment in the east districts of Sikkim is essential, for empowering students for the modern world and addressing challenges. Further, it can also serve to cater to the unique needs and characteristics of the region while preparing its students for the future.

Objectives of the Investigation : To examine how senior secondary students in East Sikkim emotionally adjust based on their gender.

1. To investigate the social adjustment of senior secondary students in East Sikkim concerning their gender.
2. To analyze the educational adjustment of senior secondary students in East Sikkim based on gender.
3. To assess the overall adjustment of senior secondary students in East Sikkim considering gender.

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses have been set up for the study.

HO₁: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to emotional adjustment.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to social adjustment.

HO₃: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to educational adjustment.

HO₃: There is no significant difference between senior secondary school boys and girls of Sikkim with regard to total adjustment.

Delimitations of the Study : The study is only looking at a particular group of students - senior secondary school students who live in East Sikkim. The study is not looking at students from other grade levels or students from other areas outside of East Sikkim. It aims to understand and gather information specifically from these groups of students.

Operational Definition of the Terms Study : Adjustment- refers to the ability to handle and maintain oneself effectively in any given situation.

Senior Secondary School Student- Students who are enrolled in the 11th and 12th grades of high school.

The Design : In this research, the survey method was employed, utilizing a descriptive research approach in the field of educational psychology. This method was deemed appropriate because it allows for the collection of evidence regarding the current situation under study. By employing surveys, researchers can obtain valuable data from a large sample of participants, enabling them to gain insights into the prevailing conditions related to the educational context or phenomenon of interest. Additionally, this approach facilitates the identification of norms or standard benchmarks, which can then be used to compare and evaluate the present positions or behaviors in the educational setting. The gathered information can serve as a foundation for devising effective plans of action, interventions, or improvements to address specific issues or enhance the overall educational experience or outcomes. By employing the survey method in educational psychology research, researchers can contribute to a better understanding of the factors influencing learning, behavior, and academic performance, ultimately leading to informed decision-making and positive advancements in the educational domain.

The Sample and Sampling Technique : In this study, 94 senior secondary school students were chosen as the sample from the East Sikkim district, and the selection process followed stratified random sampling techniques. This sampling method involves dividing the population into subgroups or strata based on specific characteristics. In this case, the students were divided into strata based on gender. Consequently, out of the 94 students in the sample, an equal number of 47 girls and 47 boys were selected from the East district of Sikkim. By using stratified random sampling, the researchers ensured that the sample represented a balanced and representative distribution of both male and female students in the senior secondary schools in that district. This approach enhances the validity and generalizability of the study's findings, as it allows for a more accurate reflection of the gender composition in the larger population of senior

The Tools : The Adjustment Inventory is a tool used for the study and this tool was created by Sinha and Singh in 2007 to help school students understand how well they are adapting to different aspects of their lives. It's a questionnaire with 60 questions that cover three main areas: "(i) emotional (ii) social and (iii) educational".

Table 1.

A Comparison of Dimensions and Total Adjustment Between Genders Among Senior Secondary School Students in The East Sikkim District. (Boy-47, Girls- 47, N=94)

S. No	Variable	Gender	Means	SD	t-Values
1.	Emotional Adjustment	Boys	8.51	2.06	0.98@

		Girls	8.57	1.92	
2.	Social Adjustment	Boys	10.06	1.74	0.24@
		Girls	9.97	1.68	
3.	Educational Adjustment	Boys	7.65	2.00	0.66@
		Girls	7.93	2.00	
4.	Total Adjustment	Boys	26.23	2.80	0.96@
		Girls	26.82	3.15	

Note: @= *Not significant*

The study looked at the differences in adjustment among boys and girls in a senior secondary school. The study focused on emotional, social, and educational adjustments, as well as overall adjustment. To understand the results, we need to look at the "t" values and compare them with the table values. The "t" value is a statistical measure used to check if there is a meaningful difference between the averages of two groups. i.e., boys and girls respectively.

The first dimension i.e., emotional adjustment, the calculated "t" value was 0.98. The table values for significance at 0.05 and 0.01 levels were 1.98 and 2.62, respectively. Since the calculated "t" value is 0.98 which is lower than the table values. So, it indicates that boys and girls have similar emotional adjustment, and “there is no significant difference between them in this aspect”.

In the second dimension i.e., social adjustment, the calculated "t" value was 0.24, which is also lower than the table values 1.98 and 2.62. Therefore, it So, it indicates that boys and girls have similar social adjustment, and there is no significant difference between them in this aspect.

In the third dimension i.e., educational adjustment, the calculated "t" value was 0.66, which is also lower than the table value of 1.98 at the 0.05 level and 2.62 at the 0.01 level. So, it indicates that boys and girls have similar educational adjustment, and “there is no significant difference between them in this aspect”.

Lastly, for the total adjustment, the calculated "t" value was 0.96. At the 0.05 level, the table value is 1.98, and at the 0.01 level, it is 2.62. Since the calculated "t" value falls between these table values, the results are not significant at the 0.01 level and not significant at the 0.05 level. Therefore, “there is so significant difference in total adjustment between boys and girls at the 0.01 level and at the 0.05 level”.

Results : The results showed that boys and girls were similar, and there were no important differences between them in terms of emotional adjustment, social adjustment, educational adjustment, and overall total adjustment in the East Sikkim district. This implies that both male and female students in the district demonstrated similar levels of adjustment in these various areas. Specifically, they showed comparable abilities to handle their emotions, interact socially, and perform well academically. Additionally, the total adjustment score, which combines all the aspects together, also showed no significant gender-based differences. These findings suggest that both boys and girls in the East Sikkim district were equally capable of adapting to their emotional, social, and academic challenges, resulting in similar overall adjustment levels. The absence of gender differences in these areas highlights the potential for a balanced and supportive

environment for students of both genders in the district, contributing to their overall well-being and academic success.

Conclusion: The conclusion of the research study indicates that emotional, social, educational adjustment, and total adjustment did not show any important differences, between boys and girls in a senior secondary school. The statistical analysis, using "t" values, showed that all the calculated "t" values were lower than the corresponding table values at both the 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. This means that the study did not find any evidence of significant variation in adjustment between boys and girls in the mentioned dimensions. In summary, the research suggests that the emotional, social, and educational adjustments of boys and girls in the senior secondary school context are comparable, and there is no significant difference in their overall adjustment.

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